

FAUNA AND DISTRIBUTION DYNAMICS OF RABBIT HELMINTHS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article is written about the study of the fauna and distribution dynamics of rabbit helminths in Uzbekistan, conducting research on rabbit helminths, introducing innovations in the field.

Keywords: rabbit helminths, fauna, distribution dynamics, viral and infectious diseases, myxomatosis, coccidiosis, vaccination.

Introduction. The local rabbit's body does not tolerate diseases, especially if they are exposed to a virus. As a result, yesterday, a completely healthy animal dies for no reason. Therefore, the condition of Rabbits should be constantly monitored, everything should be done for signs of illness and to isolate it from relatives, as well as to treat it. In this article, we will focus on common diseases that cause rabbit helminths and their death, fauna and distribution dynamics, why they appear and what to do in such cases.

A common cause of disease and subsequent death of rabbits is violation of sanitary standards in the content. The subsequent cleaning of coffee, watering with dirty or spoiled water, all this has a negative effect on the health of the population. In particular, unbalanced nutrition, which weakens the animal's immunity, has a negative effect.

Rabbits die and have a careful owner who provides them with good food, timely cleaning and disinfection of cells. This is because viral and infectious diseases are common in the summer, because they are transmitted not only from sick animals to healthy ones, but also through insect bites. The most common diseases of adults and young people:

- VGBK;
- myxomatosis;
- pasteurellosis;
- coccidiosis;
- nightingale.

UHD (fever) - a viral hemorrhagic disease of rabbits, when to vaccinate.

Abbreviation - rabbit viral hemorrhagic disease. This disease causes the death of rabbits. Animals prone to diseases for two months. VGBK, or common word fever, is highly contagious and is transmitted not only by luggage, meat and feces of infected persons, but also by air. 90% of patients die. Since UGKK can be asymptomatic, it is not always possible to look at the infection of the animal. In the infectious form, rabbits refuse to eat, become restless, quickly lose their strength and move slowly, but at the same time raise their legs, shake their legs and throw their heads.

Viral hemorrhagic disease of rabbits.

The animal is in pain, so it periodically blows through the nose, releasing possible blood pressure. Death lasts from 24 to 72 hours after infection. The disease affects and destroys the animal's liver, and also causes pulmonary edema, which is often fatal because the body is deprived of enough oxygen.

To protect your livestock, you should use a special vaccine given to 45-day-old baby rabbits. Adults may be admitted at any time. The validity period of the vaccine is one year, after which it is necessary to carry out a renewal. The treatment of the disease has not yet been developed, and the reasons for the recovery of individuals have not been determined.

Myxomatosis (distemper), visible signs.

The disease is transmitted through insect bites and causes a large amount of mucus secretion in the nose and eyes. An infected animal can live with these symptoms for a long time and can harm its relatives. Myxomatosis, common cholera, is very dangerous for young people, whose rate of aging is much faster than that of adults.

Along with the mucous membranes of rabbits affected by myxomatosis, infected individuals also have swelling or nodular swelling in the nose, ears and eyes. The incubation period lasts from 2 to 20 days, after which symptoms appear. After the onset of symptoms, the disease progresses rapidly and leads to adult animals at about 10-14 years of age and within 7 days.

Myxomatosis spreads very quickly, and if one disease agent is found on the farm, it is likely that others will already be infected. There is no effective treatment for the disease. Therefore, vaccination is necessary to prevent it. The use of an inoculated vaccine containing myxomatosis and UHDB syringe eliminates the need to cut the animal with two syringes.

Coccidiosis.

The disease is associated with parasitic protozoa of unicellular organisms. Parasites affect the liver and intestines. Every rabbit is a carrier of coccidiosis, but clinical manifestations are rare.

Coccidiosis manifests itself clearly, which helps with the diagnosis. Such a sick animal has a swollen belly and weakened body, no appetite. The disease is transmitted through coccidia oocytes present in food and water. Healthy animals with a strong immune system can independently resist the development of coccidia with painful clinical manifestations.

During the slaughter of an infected rabbit, a point light growth in the form of a nodule is observed in the liver and intestines. In addition, the liver increases 5 times. The disease is treated with antibiotics, but first of all, it is necessary to improve the conditions of detention without allowing the proliferation of filth and cell swarms.

Conclusion. It follows that rabbits are susceptible to many infections, and it is better to prevent them than to fight them. The main diseases of rabbits and their symptoms and treatment should be known to any farmer in order to help the animals in time. In addition, preventive measures should be taken.

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